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REF. NO: U.S.W.
DATE: 3RD AUGUST, 1944.

J.W. RYDE.
D. RYDE.

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ATTENUATION OF CENTIMETRE WAVES BY RAIN,
HAIL AND CLOUDS.

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This copy was made by photographing the pages of a paper copy of the original Report, using my Canon DSLR camera on a stand built for the purpose, then editing the resulting images and combining them.

The Report came to me from Peter Ryde, son of the authors John W. Ryde and his wife Dorothy, who was a first cousin of my father. She performed much of the mathematical work, and it was amongst her belongings when she died. The image quality is about the best that could be produced, given the age of the paper and its general condition, plus the fact that it was typed and printed by the wax stencil process in common use at the time.

Lex Haworth

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DIRECTOR.
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ATTENUATION OF CENTIMETRE WAVES BY RAIN,
HAIL AND CLOUDS.

This report is a continuation of previous Report No. 7831 and gives the results of computations regarding the attenuation produced by various meteorological conditions on electromagnetic radiation of wavelength between 1 and 3 cm.

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SUMMARY.

More accurate values of the refractive index and absorption index of water at centimetre wavelengths are now available. Values of the attenuation produced by rain drops of various sizes have been recomputed for $\lambda = 1.25$ and $\lambda = 3$ cm. with the new constants.

In the case of the larger drop diameters at these very short wavelengths, the series expressions developed in Report No. 7831 are not sufficiently accurate and so the exact expressions have been used whenever necessary.

To determine the attenuation in rain as a function of rate of precipitation, the drop-size distribution has been allowed for, using data given by Lenard. It is concluded that, if p is the rate of precipitation in mm. per hour, then, except possibly at low rates of rainfall, the attenuation will not exceed the following values, corresponding to room temperature.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{db/ km} &= 0.22 \cdot p & (\lambda = 1.25) \\ &= 0.06 \cdot p & (\lambda = 3) \end{aligned}$$

while for rain whose drop-size distribution is of a more usual form (Moderate Rain type) the values will be

$$\begin{aligned} \text{db/ km} &= 0.1 \cdot p & (\lambda = 1.25) \\ &= 0.03 \cdot p & (\lambda = 3) \end{aligned}$$

(These attenuation values are shown to be in good accord with the B.T.L. observations.) In round figures, once a year, p may be expected to rise, over a period of about an hour to 10 in England and 100 in Sumatra. Correspondingly higher values may be expected over shorter intervals. At $\lambda = 1.0$ all the above attenuation figures should be increased by roughly 40%.

It is shown that, in clouds and fogs, composed of water droplets, the attenuation is

db/

$$\begin{aligned} \text{db/} &= 0.287 \cdot M & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda = 1.25 \\ \lambda = 3 \end{array} \right. \\ \text{km} &= 0.056 \cdot M \end{aligned}$$

where M is the liquid water content in gm. per m³. The value of M is of the order of unity in dense clouds but may be higher in the densest fogs. These results are, for convenience, also expressed in the form of attenuation limits corresponding to a given visual range. Thus, for a visibility of 200 feet,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{db/} &= 0.12 \text{ to } 0.48 & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda = 1.25 \\ \lambda = 3 \end{array} \right. & \text{(Visual} \\ \text{km} &= 0.024 \text{ to } 0.1 & & \text{range 200 ft.)} \end{aligned}$$

Values are tabulated for visibilities between 100 and 3000 feet. All these results refer to room temperature and may need to be increased by a factor, perhaps as great as 4, when the temperature of the cloud or fog is near 0° C.

In the case of ice, the refractive and absorption indices are not so well known at the shorter wavelengths. Provisional computations have, however, been carried out with the best data available at the moment. No data is available regarding the rate of precipitation in hailstorms although it is possible to estimate a limit which would very rarely be exceeded.

The corresponding maximum attenuation for hailstorms is derived for cases in which the stone diameters vary from 0.1 up to 2.5 cm.

In the case of stones 1 cm. in diameter, for example, it is found that the probable maximum attenuation, corresponding to the heaviest falls, is about 60 db./km. at $\lambda = 1.25$ and 3 db./km. at $\lambda = 3$. For a diameter of 0.3 cm. the values are 3.3 and 0.18 db./km. respectively.

Comparing the heaviest falls of hail with the heaviest rain, it is found that the attenuation in each case is the same if the hailstone diameter is 0.7 cm. at $\lambda = 1.25$. and 1.4 cm. at $\lambda = 3$.

If, as is possible, the hailstones are coated with a water layer, the attenuation produced is likely to be greater still.

A study has also been made of the attenuation due to clouds composed of ice crystals. It is shown that the attenuation produced by a given mass of ice, subdivided into small spicules, discs or spherules, is greatest for the disc form. It is found that the attenuation is then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{db/} &= 0.013 \cdot M & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda = 1.25 \\ \lambda = 3 \end{array} \right. \\ \text{km} &= 0.005 \cdot M \end{aligned}$$

where M may be taken as 0.5 for the more dense ice clouds although it may often be 0.1 or less.

It is concluded that, in general, the attenuation due to ice crystal clouds will be only of the order of one hundredth that due to water droplet clouds.

The effect of temperature in changing the refractive and absorption indices of water has been considered. The only data available at the moment is that of B

of Keppel for $\lambda = 3.7$ cm. From work being carried out at the N.P.L. it would, however, seem likely that the temperature change of the indices published by Keppel is somewhat high. Until the new values become available, we have assumed Keppel's values, which lead to the following:-

In the case of small water droplets, the attenuation at $\lambda = 3.7$ increases by a factor of 4.2 for a temperature change from 30° C. to 5° C. For larger droplets the effect is probably less.

Lastly, estimates of the attenuation in clouds and fogs are given for the millimetre band.

1. INTRODUCTION.

At the request of the Ultra Short Wave Panel Working Committee, the computations reported here were carried out to provide as definite information as possible on the attenuation effects, produced by various meteorological conditions, on radiation having wavelengths in the range of 1 to 3 cm.

The whole subject was dealt with in Report No. 7831 which gave a general picture of all the effects and their order of magnitude between 1 and 100 cm.

Since the abovementioned report was written, more accurate data has become available regarding the values of the refractive index and absorption index of water. Also, since the effects increase at the shorter wavelengths, it is desirable to determine their values more accurately.

This report covers attenuation effects only but echo intensities and refraction effects will, it is hoped, be dealt with later.

Series which enormously ease the labour of computation were developed in Report No. 7831 and were there used exclusively. For the larger diameter droplets and wavelengths below 3 to 5 cm. the three term series ceases to be sufficiently accurate; further terms were therefore derived. But, for the above conditions, the series converges very slowly so that the new terms were still not adequate; they are, however, of value in showing just how far the 3-term series can be used with accuracy. In view of this position, a few values have, in each case, been determined from the original expressions of Mie, in spite of the considerable labour of computation. The curve determined from the 3 or 6 term series, for the small values of D/λ , was then extrapolated to pass through the exact points at the higher values.

In the previous report the attenuation in the case of rain was given for typical values of drop diameter D , measured in cm., and of N the number of drops per cubic centimetre of air. For greater precision the data here are first given for various values of D assuming $N = 1$, and then, by means of known typical drop-size distributions in different classes of rain, the attenuation in db./km. is given in terms of the rate of rainfall in mm./hr. for each main class

It may be noted that, so long as the concentration of droplets is not so high that the distance between the drops is less than about five of their diameters, the db. loss per km. may be taken as directly proportional to N . This holds for all the cases we shall need to consider here.

2. VALUES OF THE REFRACTIVE AND ABSORPTION INDICES.

The values of the refractive and absorption indices n and χ employed in the previous report were obtained, for water, by plotting the, somewhat scattered, published values against the wavelength λ . At the shorter wavelengths only very approximate values could be obtained. Since then, however, at $\lambda=1.25$, new and more accurate values have been measured at the Clarendon Laboratory and at the N.P.L. Based on these measurements the values adopted are for $\lambda = 1.25$, $n = 6.4$, $n\chi = 3.0$ while for $\lambda = 3$, the previous values, $n = 7.9$ and $n\chi = 2.0$ are retained. In both cases the values refer to a temperature of about 18°C .

As regards ice, estimates of echo intensities only could be given in Report No. 7831 because no data was available for $n\chi$. Soon after that report was written Professor Willis Jackson⁽¹⁾ obtained, for ice, the values $n = 1.48$ and $n\chi = 0.0027$ at $\lambda = 9.4 \text{ cm}$. Consideration of Figure 4 of Report No. 7831 shows that it is unlikely that n will differ much from 1.48 as the wavelength decreases to 1 cm. It would also seem unlikely that the order of magnitude of $n\chi$ would change over the same range. Until the results of measurements are available we shall therefore adopt the above values for the wavelengths with which we are here concerned.

3. EXPRESSION FOR THE ATTENUATION.

The attenuation of a parallel beam, traversing a thickness x of a suspension of droplets may be expressed by

$$I = I_0 e^{-\sigma x} \quad \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

in which σ is given by

$$\sigma = \frac{N\lambda^2}{2\pi} \alpha^3 \left\{ c_1 + c_2 \alpha^2 + c_3 \alpha^3 + \dots \right\} \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

where λ is the wavelength in the suspending medium, in the present case air, and

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi D}{\lambda} \quad \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

if the refractive index of air be taken as unity.

The c coefficients in (2) are functions of

$$g = n^2 (1 - \chi^2) \quad \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

and

$$h = 2n^2 \chi \quad \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

which/

(1) Willis Jackson, M.of S., D.S.R. Extra Mural Research
F.72/76, Report No. 31, November 1941.

which are, respectively, the real and imaginary parts of the generalised dielectric constant. Then, as shown in the previous report, the first three coefficients are given by

$$c_1 = \frac{6R}{(g+2)^2 + R^2} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{R}{15} + \frac{5R}{3[(2g+3)^2 + R^2]} + \frac{6R[(g+2)(7g-10) + 7R^2]}{5[(g+2)^2 + R^2]^2} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

$$c_3 = \frac{4}{3} \frac{(g-1)^2(g+2)^2 + R^2 \{2(g-1)(g+2) - 9\} + R^4}{[(g+2)^2 + R^2]^2} \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

For the values of n and χ which concern us here the above 3 terms are adequate for small values of $n\alpha$ but when this product approaches unity, further terms are required. As $n\alpha$ rises above unity the series (2) soon becomes only very slowly convergent and the fundamental expressions (12) to (15) of Report No. 7831 must be used. This has been done here whenever necessary.

Since the db. attenuation corresponding to an intensity ratio I/I_0 is given by

$$10 \log_{10} \frac{I}{I_0} = 4.343 \ln \frac{I}{I_0} = 4.343 \sigma x \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

then if cm. units are used for D and λ , the attenuation expressed in the form of decibels per kilometre is given by

$$\frac{dk}{km} = 4.343 \cdot 10^5 \sigma \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

Hence

$$\frac{dk}{km} = 4.343 \cdot 10^5 \frac{N\lambda^2}{2\pi} \alpha^3 f(\alpha, n, \chi) \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

or, by (3),

$$\frac{dk}{km} = 4.343 \cdot 10^5 N \frac{\pi D^2}{4} 2\alpha f(\alpha, n, \chi) \dots\dots\dots(12)$$

where we have written

$$f(\alpha, n, \chi) = c_1 + c_2 \alpha^2 + c_3 \alpha^3 + \dots \dots\dots(13)$$

The form (12) is interesting. For assume that the drops are indefinitely large compared with the wavelength and that they absorb all the energy they intercept. Then, provided that they are not so closely spaced as to overlap, the attenuation produced will obviously be

db./

(12) Inadvertently, the third term of (7) was given incorrectly in the previous report. For values of n as large as for water the correction makes a quite negligible difference to the numerical results since the first term of (7) is then by far the largest.

$$dlr/km = 4.343 \cdot 10^5 N \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

so that, by (12)

$$2 \alpha f(\alpha, n, x)$$

is the correction factor to be applied to the simple geometrical optics case for indefinitely large, completely absorbing spheres.

When α is sufficiently small for the second and third terms of (13) to be neglected in comparison with the first, then (11) reduces to

$$dlr/km = 4.0932 \frac{M}{\lambda} c, \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

in which

$$M = 10^5 \frac{\pi}{6} N D^3 \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

is the total volume of the drops contained in one cubic metre of air. In the particular case of water, having unit density, M is the mass of drops in grams per cubic metre of air.

Thus, whenever the first term is predominant, we need only to consider the value of M and not of N and D individually.

4. ATTENUATION BY PARTICLES OF SHAPE OTHER THAN SPHERICAL.

When investigating the case of clouds composed of ice crystals we shall need to consider the effect of a departure from the spherical shape assumed by water droplets. Ice crystals occur in the form of spicules, stars and platelets, the scattering power and absorption of which are likely to differ appreciably from that of spherules.

Now, Gans (3) has treated the case of ellipsoidal particles on the same lines as Mie's exact theory for spheres, but has worked it out only for the case of particles whose dimensions are very small compared with the wavelength.

From this work we have derived the following expressions, in terms of our g and h, for the cases of needles and discs. These have been derived from the limiting expressions for prolate and oblate ellipsoids when the axial ratios tend to zero.

In this way we find that, if the crystals are oriented at random, then over the range for which (15) is valid, the value of c, given in (6) for spherules should be replaced by (17) and (18) below in the case of needles and discs respectively.

$c_1/$

(3) R.Gans. Ann.d.Phys. 37, 881 (1912).

$$C_1 = \frac{2h}{9} \left[1 + \frac{8}{(g+1)^2 + h^2} \right] \quad (\text{Needles}) \dots\dots\dots(17)$$

$$C_1 = \frac{2h}{9} \left[2 + \frac{1}{g^2 + h^2} \right] \quad (\text{Discs}) \dots\dots\dots(18)$$

5. THE ATTENUATION DUE TO WATER DROPLETS WHEN THERE IS ONE DROPLET PER CM.³.

Taking the values of the refractive and absorption indices given in Section (2) we find the values of the coefficients given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Values of the Constants and Coefficients for Water at 18° C.

	$\lambda = 1.25$	$\lambda = 3$
n	6.4	7.9
$n \times$	3.0	2.0
g	31.96	58.41
h	38.4	31.6
C_1	0.0877	0.0409
C_2	2.683	2.163
C_3	1.231	1.238

Three terms of the series (2) with these values are found to give accurate results up to about $D = 0.1$ cm. for the wavelength range which interests us here. For larger values of D the fundamental expressions must be used.

In the case of $\lambda = 1.25$ it is found that the 3-term series gives values about 25% too high at $D = 0.2$ and they are about 5 times too great at $D = 0.5$.

In the case of $\lambda = 3$ the 3-term series first falls below the exact values; it is sensibly correct up to $D = 0.07$ after which it falls off until at $D = 0.3$ it is some 3 times too low. After this the error decreases and the values coincide at $D = 0.55$; at still higher values of D the 3-term series gives results higher than the exact expression.

Curves were plotted of the log. of the attenuation against D and the portion over which the 3-term series is valid was extrapolated through points for larger values of D determined from the exact expressions. On the log. scale the deviations are not large.

From these curves, values of the attenuation were read for values of D in steps of 0.05 cm. The results are given in Table II. When glancing at these values, which are for $N = 1$, it should be borne in mind that in rain storms N is

of the order of 10^{-4} .

It must also be remembered that the computations are based on the experimental values of the refractive and absorption indices determined at 18° C. Some correction needs to be applied when the temperature of the rain differs much from this value, see Section (12).

The Table is not continued beyond $D = 0.55$ cm. since this is the diameter of the largest rain drop that can remain stable while falling through the atmosphere; any larger drop would immediately break up into smaller ones.

TABLE II.

Attenuation due to Water Droplets at
Concentration of One Droplet per cm.³
($N = 1$). (Temperature 18° C.)

D cm.	db. per km. for $N = 1$	
	$\lambda = 1.25$	$\lambda = 3.0$
0.55	4.37 10^5	1.18 10^5
.5	3.31 10^5	9.33 10^4
.45	2.46 10^5	6.61 10^4
.4	1.59 10^5	4.68 10^4
.35	9.33 10^4	2.89 10^4
.3	4.90 10^4	1.62 10^4
.25	2.19 10^4	7.08 10^3
.2	8.23 10^3	2.40 10^3
.15	2.46 10^3	5.63 10^2
.1	4.17 10^2	6.61 10
.05	2.69 10	3.99
.01	1.53 10^{-1}	2.97 10^{-2}

6. PROVISIONAL VALUES OF THE ATTENUATION DUE TO HAILSTONES

ASSUMING $N = 1$.

The values of the constants, adopted provisionally, for ice and those of the corresponding coefficients are given in Table III. As discussed in Section (2) the same values are assumed to hold at both wavelengths. Actually it is to be expected that χ will vary somewhat but it will probably remain of the same order of magnitude.

TABLE /

TABLE III.

Values of the Constants and Coefficients adopted, provisionally, for Ice.

	$\lambda = 1.0$ to 10.0 cm.
n	1.48
$n \times$	0.0027
g	2.19
h	0.0080
C_1	0.00274
C_2	0.00277
C_3	0.108

Following the same procedure as described in the last Section we find that the 3 term series is very accurate as far as $D = 0.5$ for $\lambda = 1.25$ and to $D = 1.1$ for $\lambda = 3$. Beyond these values the results are based on computations from the exact expressions. Values interpolated for a series of hailstone diameters are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Attenuation due to Hailstones at a Concentration of One Stone per cm.^3 ($N = 1$). (Provisional Values).

D cm.	db. per km. for $N = 1$	
	$\lambda = 1.25$	$\lambda = 3$
2.5	-	$1.00 \cdot 10^7$
2.0	-	$3.30 \cdot 10^6$
1.5	-	$7.94 \cdot 10^5$
1.0	$1.99 \cdot 10^6$	$9.55 \cdot 10^4$
.8	$4.90 \cdot 10^5$	$2.51 \cdot 10^4$
.6	$1.12 \cdot 10^5$	$4.79 \cdot 10^3$
.5	$4.47 \cdot 10^4$	$1.70 \cdot 10^3$
.4	$1.23 \cdot 10^4$	$5.13 \cdot 10^2$
.3	$2.29 \cdot 10^3$	$1.26 \cdot 10^2$
.2	$2.29 \cdot 10^2$	2.24 10
.1	7.94	2.24

Before proceeding further we must consider the drop size distribution in rain and hailstorms.

7. SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF DROPS IN RAIN.

In a memorandum to the U.S.W. Panel Working Committee A.C. Best has provided a compilation of data on the number of drops of various sizes which fall per square metre during a number of rain storms. The size distribution can be deduced by dividing by the terminal velocity v in metres per second.

The rate of precipitation p , for any given D , is easily shown to be given by

$$\begin{aligned} p &= 3.6 M v && \text{mm. per hour} \\ &= 1.885 10^6 v N D^3 && \dots\dots\dots(19) \end{aligned}$$

Values of p in mm. per hour for $N = 1$ are given, together with values of v , in Table V.

TABLE V.

Terminal Velocity and Rate
of Precipitation in mm./hr.
for $N = 1$.

D cm.	v m. per sec.	p for $N = 1$ mm. per hr.
0.55	8.15	2.56 10^6
.5	8.0	1.89 10^6
.45	7.85	1.35 10^6
.4	7.7	9.25 10^5
.35	7.35	5.90 10^5
.3	6.9	3.51 10^5
.25	6.4	1.89 10^5
.2	5.9	8.90 10^4
.15	5.2	3.32 10^4
.1	4.4	8.30 10^3
.05	3.1	7.30 10^2

Of the various sets of data given by Best we choose that of Lenard as covering the greatest range of conditions. The data was divided into three groups associated with 'Moderate', 'Heavy' and 'Excessive' rain conditions according to Humphreys classification. These groups are given in Tables VI, VII and VIII. In each case the drop size distribution is given for each occurrence together with the mean distribution for the group.

Values of $N \cdot 10^6$ and of M , the latter computed from/

from (16), are given as well as the observed rate of precipitation in each individual case. The mean observed rate of precipitation is given for the group, together with that calculated from the mean distribution by summing the contributions for each D interval using (19).

For comparison the data given by Humphreys (Physics of the Air) as being typical of each class of rain is also included.

TABLE VI.

Drop Size Distributions
"Moderate Rain".

D cm.	Number of Drops per m. ³ in each D Interval.				Mean Values.	Humphreys' Typical Values.
0.05	515	320	41.5	19	224	D = 0.1
.1	27	45.5	23	64	40	
.15	11.5	27	14	31	21	
.2	34	24	17	3.4	19	
.25	-	-	4.5	3.1	2	
.3	-	-	8.2	-	2	
.35	-	-	-	-	-	
.4	-	-	-	-	-	
.45	-	-	-	-	-	
.5	-	-	-	-	-	
N.10 ⁶	588	417	108	121	308	530
p.obs. mm./hr.	3.6	5.4	6.6	3.0	3.99 calc. 4.65 obs.	4.0
M gm./m. ³	0.21	0.19	0.26	0.13	0.20	0.28

It will be seen that the predominant diameter in the last of the four cases coincides with Humphreys' typical value, but in the other cases it is smaller. The values of p and M are in quite good agreement with Humphreys 'Moderate Rain' class.

TABLE VII/

TABLE VII.
Drop Size Distribution
'Heavy Rain'.

D cm.	No. per m. ³ in each D Interval.	Humphreys' Typical Values.
0.05	218	D = 0.15
.1	119	
.15	67	
.2	50	
.25	32	
.3	11.7	
.35	3.8	
.4	2.6	
.45	-	
.5	-	
N.10 ⁶	504	470
ρ mm./hr.	22.4 calc. 20.4 obs.	15
M	0.99	0.83

In the case of 'Heavy Rain', Table VII, the agreement of the figures for N, ρ and M with Humphreys' typical values is good but the predominant diameter is low.

Lastly, corresponding to Humphreys' class designated 'Excessive Rain', we have the distributions shown in Table VIII. The first of the four cases in this group was for sudden rain from a comparatively small cloud, the second for violent rain, like a cloudburst, while the other two are respectively for the heaviest period and for the end of a particularly violent storm. In general, these distributions may be taken to be representative of heavy thunderstorms.

TABLE VIII/

TABLE VIII.

Drop Size Distributions.
'Excessive Rain'.

D cm.	Number of drops per m. ³ in each D Interval.				Mean Values.	Humphreys' Typical Values.
0.05	-	32	165	2.2	50	D = 0.21
.1	11	295	96	53	114	
.15	9.7	97	69	22	50	
.2	26	34	23	7.8	23	
.25	-	-	24	1.1	6.2	
.3	29	-	20	-	12.2	
.35	-	-	-	4.8	1.2	
.4	6.5	-	-	5.1	2.9	
.45	-	25.5	11.4	-	9.3	
.5	-	-	-	3.1	0.8	
N.10 ⁶	83	484	408	99	269	380
p.obs. mm./hr.	19.2	43.2	34.2	15.6	27.5 calc. 28.1 obs.	40
M	0.76	1.66	1.30	0.58	1.09	1.85

It will be seen that the predominant diameter is 0.3 cm. in the first case and 0.1 in the others, while Humphreys' typical diameter is 0.21. N, ρ and M are somewhat lower than Humphreys gives for typical 'Excessive Rain'.

Humphreys also includes a class designated 'Cloudburst' for which the predominant diameter is 0.3 cm., N.10⁶ = 380, ρ = 100 and M = 5.4. None of Lenard's cases approaches these values of ρ and M but the first of the four distributions in Table VIII has a maximum at D = 0.3 and probably would represent this class if the values of N, ρ and M were suitably increased.

8. THE ATTENUATION DUE TO RAIN.

In Report No. 7831 we assumed, for simplicity, that for each class of rain, the drops were all of one size, corresponding to the typical diameters given by Humphreys. By the use of the averaged drop size distributions, given in the last Section, we shall here be able to obtain relations between the attenuation and the rate of precipitation for each class of rain. For any one class, the attenuation is proportional to N and therefore to ρ the rate of precipitation. Let us write,

$$\text{db./km.} = k \cdot \rho \quad \dots\dots\dots(20)$$

where ρ is in mm./hr. and k is a constant depending on the particular drop size distribution. It will be seen that k is the attenuation for a precipitation rate of 1 mm./hr.

Summing the contribution to the attenuation from each interval in the mean distributions and dividing by the calculated value of ρ , given in the column of mean values in Tables VI, VII and VIII, we obtain k for each of the three classes.

Instead of the 'Cloudburst' class mentioned at the end of the last section we shall take the particular distribution which, for a given rate of precipitation and wavelength, will give the maximum attenuation; that is, the optimum size distribution giving the greatest value of k .

At first sight it might be thought that, since, over the range investigated, the attenuation steadily increases with drop diameter, the optimum distribution would be one in which all the drops are of the greatest possible stable diameter $D = 0.55$ cm. It is true that this applies when N is constant but, if we allow N and D to vary in such a way as to keep ρ constant, the result is different.

Thus, for each D , dividing the attenuation given in Table II by the corresponding value of ρ in Table V, we obtain a series of values of k . In this way we find that the maximum k occurs when $D = 0.45$ for $\lambda = 1.25$ and when $D = 0.4$ when $\lambda = 3$.

It follows that if, in each case, all the drops have the above optimum diameter, the attenuation produced will be a maximum.

The corresponding maximum values of k are given in Table IX together with the k values for each of the three classes of rain. For comparison, the Table includes k values deduced from the results of some 60 observations carried out in America by the Bell Telephone Laboratories (4).

For this comparison it was necessary to determine values for $\lambda = 1$ by extrapolation; the resulting predicted figures are enclosed in brackets.

TABLE IX/

(4)

- S.D. Robertson, Report MM.42-160-87 Aug. (1942).
 S.D. Robertson and A.P. King. LA. 42-160-93 Aug. (1942).
 S.D. Robertson, Report MM.43-160-2. Jan. (1943).

TABLE IX.

Values of k in Relation (20).
 k is the attenuation in db./km.
 for a rate of precipitation of 1 mm./hr.

Drop Size Distribution Characteristic of:-	$\lambda = 1$ (Extrapolated)	$\lambda = 1.25$	$\lambda = 3.0$
Maximum attenuation	(0.25)	0.18	0.051
Excessive rain	(0.21)	0.15	0.044
Heavy rain	(0.15)	0.12	0.037
Moderate rain	(0.13)	0.09	0.027
Observations:-			
B.T.L. 'Max.'	0.27	-	0.056
B.T.L. Mean	0.19	-	0.03
Clarendon Mean*	0.15	-	-

The B.T.L. observations were plotted against ρ and a mean line drawn through the points; the slope of this line is quoted in Table IX as B.T.L. Mean. The value designated B.T.L. 'Max.' represents a line which is not exceeded by any observations except four at the smallest rates of precipitation.

Exact agreement would not be expected since, for example, the possible temperature effect, see Section (12), could not be allowed for. The concordance is, however, very good and gives weight to the values of the attenuation computed for other meteorological conditions detailed below and for which no observations are available.

It may be concluded that, except possibly at low rates of rainfall, the attenuation will not exceed the following values, which are the maxima of Table IX increased by 20% for safety.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{db./km.} &= 0.22 \rho & (\lambda = 1.25) \\ &= 0.06 \rho & (\lambda = 3) \end{aligned} \right\} \text{(Large drops) } \dots\dots\dots(21)$$

Also, for rain whose drop size distribution corresponds with what we have designated 'Moderate Rain', see Table VI, the attenuation will be approximately

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{db./km.} &= 0.1 \rho & (\lambda = 1.25) \\ &= 0.03 \rho & (\lambda = 3) \end{aligned} \right\} \dots\dots\dots(22)$$

As regards the values of ρ , a general idea can be obtained from the following few representative values taken from the much more complete data given in the memorandum by Best.

* Clarendon Report, C.L.Misc.3.

Once a year ρ may be expected to rise, for a period as long as one hour, to 11 mm./hr. in England and Wales, to 32 at Bucharest, to about 60 in Borneo and Java and to 84 in Sumatra.

Correspondingly higher values may be expected to occur over shorter intervals. Thus, even in England, once in ten years ρ may rise to 131 for a period of 5 minutes.

On the other hand, for moderate rain conditions, a quite usual value of ρ would be 4 and this might persist for several hours.

9. ATTENUATION DUE TO CLOUDS AND FOGS. (WATER DROPLETS).

In this Section we shall consider fogs and clouds, composed of fine water droplets, and from which no precipitation takes place. The clouds might, for example, be Stratus or Fine Weather Cumulus. In all these cases the predominant diameter of the drops will lie between about 0.0005 and 0.003 cm.

With the values of the refractive and absorption indices for water at our wavelengths we find that, for α not exceeding about 0.025, all terms in (2), except the first, can be neglected. Hence (15) is valid for these cases and there will be no need to consider the drop size distribution; only the total liquid water content is relevant.

Using the constants of Table I we find that (15) becomes

$$\text{db./km.} = 0.287 M \quad (\lambda = 1.25) \quad \dots\dots\dots(23)$$

and $\quad \quad \quad = 0.056 M \quad (\lambda = 3)$

The value of M in different clouds and fogs can vary over a wide range. Humphreys⁽⁵⁾ quotes 2.39 for dense Stratus cloud while Best quotes aeroplane measurements which frequently gave values of 0.1 to 0.3, but few above 0.5. On the other hand Houghton⁽⁶⁾ gives measured values of 0.5 to 1.5 in clouds at the summit of Mt. Washington. Best, in his memorandum, suggests that M be taken as 1.0 for cloud.

As regards fog, Humphreys quotes 0.63 for dense sea fog while Houghton measured a number of values at Round Hill, Massachusetts, from 0.2 downwards. Others in denser fogs, judged by visibility, record many values of the order of 1.0 and some between 1.0 and 4.5. Although these higher values above 1.0 may be suspect, it is a fact that, on Radford's⁽⁷⁾ plot of $\log M : \log$ visibility, they fall on a continuation of a straight line through the points
found/

(5) Humphreys. Physics of the Air.

(6) Houghton. J.Aeronautical Sci. 6, 408 (1939).

(7) Radford. Papers on Phys.Oceanography and Met.M.I.T. and Wood's Hole. Inst. Vol.6, No.4, p.19 (1938).

found by other observers.

In some instances it may be useful to know the probable range of attenuation associated with a given visual range, particularly in the case of fogs. This is reasonable for, if we refer to Redford's plot, mentioned above, which includes about 50 observations by several observers, we find that, in spite of the fact that visual range is a function of both N and D , some 95% of the points lie between $\frac{1}{3}$ and 2 times the mean M for any given visual range.

If S be the visual range measured in feet then we find that the mean line through all the observed points is given by

$$M = 1660 S^{-a} \quad \dots\dots\dots(24)$$

in which $a = 1.43$. It may be noted that the observations range over values of M from 0.015 to 4.5 gm./m.³.

From (23) and (24) we then see that the mean attenuation will be given by

$$\log_{10} \text{ db./km.} = b - 1.43 \log_{10} S \quad \dots\dots\dots(25)$$

where the constant b is 2.68 for $\lambda = 1.25$ and is 1.98 for $\lambda = 3$. Also, from the above remark, it follows that the attenuation will be expected to lie between one half and double this mean value in about 95% of cases. Values of these probable limits are given below in Table X.

TABLE X.

Probable limits of Attenuation in db.
per km. for given Visual range. (Temp. 18° C.)

Visual Range in Cloud or Fog.	Mean M gm./m. ³	db. loss per km.	
		$\lambda = 1.25$	$\lambda = 3$.
100 feet	2.3	0.32 - 1.30	0.065 - 0.26
200	0.85	0.12 - 0.48	0.024 - 0.096
300	0.48	0.068 - 0.27	0.014 - 0.056
400	0.32	0.045 - 0.18	0.009 - 0.036
500	0.23	0.033 - 0.13	0.007 - 0.026
750	0.13	0.019 - 0.075	0.004 - 0.015
1000	0.085	0.012 - 0.048	0.002 - 0.010
2000	0.032	0.005 - 0.018	0.001 - 0.004
3000	0.018	0.003 - 0.010	0.0005 - 0.002

We shall now proceed to consider the cases of hailstorms and of clouds composed of ice crystals.

10. THE ATTENUATION DUE TO HAILSTORMS.

No observational data appears to be available regarding the size distribution of hail nor, unfortunately, what is more important, regarding typical values of N .

As regards size distribution it is, however, a matter of common observation that the size of the stones falling at any given time is fairly uniform. In respect of N , Best states that the precipitation would be unlikely to exceed five times the equivalent of 4 inches of rainfall per hour. Thus an upper limit to β would be 500 mm./hr.

Given β we can find N from (19) if we know v . This we have taken from Table (5) for the range of D there given; beyond this we have extrapolated. It is to be expected that v for hailstones may differ somewhat from the value for water drops particularly at the higher D values. This is because the large drops tend to deform. From the nature of the problem, however, it is unnecessary to know the values of v to a greater accuracy than that of N , so that until accurate observations of N are forthcoming the above procedure regarding v is quite adequate.

From Table IV we can now determine the values of the attenuation for $\beta = 500$, the maximum to be expected. The average values may well be much less. Table XI gives the results.

TABLE XI.

The Maximum Attenuation to be expected from Dry Hailstones. $\beta = 500$.
(Provisional Values).

D cm.	Maximum db./km.	
	= 1.25	= 3
2.5		19.0
2.0		12.2
1.5		7.1
1.0	61.6	3.0
.8	29.9	1.5
.6	16.5	0.7
.5	11.8	0.45
.4	6.7	0.28
.3	3.3	0.18
.2	1.3	0.13
.1	0.5	0.14

These figures may be compared with the maximum we have deduced for rain. Thus, taking a value of $\rho = 100$ as a fairly extreme value for rain, (21) then gives attenuations of 22 db./km. at $\lambda = 1.25$ and 6 db./km. at $\lambda = 3$ cm. These will be seen to correspond with the maximum produced by hailstorms in which the diameters of the stones are 0.7 and 1.4 cm. in the two cases respectively.

It may be noted that as there is no instability restriction on the size of hailstones, as there is for rain drops, the larger possible diameters and larger N values associated with hailstorms can more than make up for the smaller attenuation due to ice.

All the above attenuation values assume that the ice is dry. If, as is possible, the hailstones are coated with a water layer the attenuation produced is likely to be greater still.

Hailstones can occur with diameters far exceeding the largest given in Table XI. Thus from Best's memorandum, it appears that, of reports on hailstorms in India, the most frequent diameter was in the range 0 - 1.2 cm. but on 8.9% of occasions D fell between 5 and 10 cm. while in 2.6% of storms the value of D exceeded 10 cm. (4 inches).

In view of the heavy computational work required in the case of large diameters, it was decided to leave the consideration of these until accurate measurements are available on the refractive and absorption indices.

11. THE ATTENUATION DUE TO CLOUDS COMPOSED OF ICE CRYSTALS.

We shall now consider the case of clouds composed of ice crystals. The crystals may occur in the form of stars, plates, prisms or prismatic needles, according to the conditions under which they are formed; each tends to have an hexagonal cross section. These shapes approximate, however, to discs on the one hand and to needles on the other. The attenuation produced by particles of both these forms has been treated in Section (4).

Using the provisional values of the constants given in Table III we find that (15) will be accurate for values of α up to about 0.1 and that the error will not exceed about 15% for $\alpha = 0.15$, which corresponds to $D = 0.15$ and $D = 0.06$ cm. at $\lambda = 3$ and $\lambda = 1.25$ respectively.

From Best's memorandum, it appears that, if melted, the crystals in clouds would form drops of diameter about 0.02 cm. so that we may safely use (15) and consider only the total volume M of the particles per cubic metre.

From (17) and (18) we find that for ice needles, oriented at random, $C_1 = 0.00318$ while for discs the value is 0.00393. For spherules, on the other hand, the value is 0.00274.

Thus the attenuation produced by a given mass of ice is greater when it is subdivided into discs or spherules than when it is in the form of needles. If their principal dimensions are comparable there will, of course, be many more discs or needles than spheres.

Table XII gives the corresponding values of the attenuation in terms of M.

TABLE XII.

Attenuation due to Ice Crystal Clouds.

Crystal Form	Attenuation in db./km.	
	$\lambda = 1.25$	$\lambda = 3$
Stars, Plates (Discs)	0.0129 M	0.00537 M
Spicules (Needles)	.0104 M	.00434 M
Spherules	.0090 M	.00373 M

As regards the value of M, Best states that a value of $M = 0.5$ is rarely exceeded in ice crystal clouds and it may often be less than 0.1 grams per cubic metre.

These values may be compared with the result (23) for water droplet clouds and fogs which, as we have seen, may have M values ranging from 4.5 to below 0.015.

On the whole, it may be expected that the attenuation due to ice crystal clouds will be only of the order of one hundredth that due to clouds composed of water droplets.

As in the last Section we must emphasise that the above results assume that the ice crystals are dry; the attenuation will increase if they are partially melted or coated with a water film.

12. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE.

Temperature can only affect the results through a change of n and χ . Little data on these changes is available at the moment, apart from that due to Kebbel (8) for $\lambda = 3.7$. Values from his curve are given in Table XIII together with the values interpolated for $\lambda = 3.7$ from the curves, Figure 1, of Report No. 7831.

It is hoped that the results of new measurements will shortly become available but, meanwhile, we shall assume Kebbel's values in order to estimate the effect on the attenuation due to water droplets. The resulting values of the c coefficients are given in Table XIII.

TABLE/

(8) W.Kebbel. Hochfrequenztechnik und Electroakustik
53, 81 (1939).

TABLE XIII.

Variation of Constants with Temperature.
Water. $\lambda = 3.7$ cm.

Source and Temp.	n	$n\chi$	C_1	C_2	C_3
Kebbel 5° C.	4.18	1.23	0.1477	0.868	1.009
Kebbel 15° C.	6.5	1.87	.0643	1.713	1.191
Kebbel 30° C.	8.0	1.71	.0348	1.871	1.226
Report 7831. 'Room'	8.2	1.70	.0409	2.163	1.238

When the water droplets are very small, as is the case in clouds and fogs, then by (15) the attenuation is directly proportional to C_1 . It follows that, if Kebbel's values are correct, a decrease of temperature from 30° C. to 5° C. would increase the attenuation as much as 4.25 times. It may be, however, that this factor is on the high side.

As the droplet diameter increases to values such that the 3 term series must be used, the effect of temperature diminishes. This is because, for larger diameters, the second and third terms with coefficients C_2 and C_3 become important. But C_3 varies little with temperature while C_2 varies in the opposite direction to C_1 so that the changes tend to compensate.

For still larger diameters, corresponding to the larger rain drops, we have seen that the exact expressions must be used. It is proposed to do this as soon as the new measurements of n and χ are available.

13. ESTIMATES OF THE ATTENUATION IN THE MILLIMETRE BAND.

In this Section we shall first of all show that the values of n and $n\chi$ recently determined, at wavelengths between 1 and 2 cm., together with the fairly well determined values at 5 cm. and above, all fit surprisingly well with those calculated on the simple dipole theory of Debye⁽⁹⁾. This agreement had been noted by Dr. Collie of the Clarendon Laboratory, but here we shall use the Debye theory to predict values in the millimetre band.

Thus, let us take the static dielectric constant ϵ_s of water as 81 and the optical refractive index $\sqrt{\epsilon_\infty}$ as 1.33. We then find that, for the particular wavelength such that

$$n = \left[\frac{\epsilon_s + \epsilon_\infty}{2} \right]^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots (26)$$

that is $n = 6.42$, the expressions below predict the values of $\chi = 0.466$ and $n\chi = 2.995$. But the Clarendon Laboratory values, measured at $\lambda = 1.26$, are $n = 6.4$, $\chi = 0.47$ and $n\chi = 3.0$, in excellent agreement.

We/

(9) P. Debye. Polar Molecules. Chap. 5.

We note that, according to these measurements, the particular condition (26) holds at $\lambda = 1.26$ for water at 18°C .

Now, on Debye's theory, our g and h are given by

$$g = \epsilon_0 + \frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_0}{1 + \frac{k^2}{\lambda^2}} \dots\dots\dots(27)$$

$$h = \frac{k}{\lambda} (g - \epsilon_0) \dots\dots\dots(28)$$

while,

$$\chi = \left[1 + \left(\frac{g}{h} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} - \frac{g}{h} \dots\dots\dots(29)$$

and

$$n = \left(\frac{k}{2\chi} \right)^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots(30)$$

In the expressions for g and h the constant k is given by

$$k = \alpha \lambda_1 \dots\dots\dots(31)$$

where λ_1 is the particular wavelength at which (26) holds and α , can be determined from the relation

$$2\alpha^2 = a + \sqrt{4 + a^2} \dots\dots\dots(32)$$

in which

$$a = \frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_0}{\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_0} \dots\dots\dots(33)$$

With the values $\epsilon_1 = 81$ and $\epsilon_0 = (1.33)^2 = 1.77$ we find $\alpha = 0.958$ and $\lambda_1 = 1.26$. But, as noted above, from the Clarendon measurements $\lambda_1 = 1.26$ so that $k = 1.59$.

From (27) to (30) we then obtain the predicted values given in Table XIV together with corresponding observations. The observed values designated 'Report 7831' are those read from the smoothed curves, through points by many observers, given in Figure 1 of that report.

TABLE/

TABLE XIV.

Predicted and Observed Values
of n and $n\chi$ for water at approximately 18° C.

λ cm.	Predicted		Observed		Source
	n	$n\chi$	n	$n\chi$	
1.26	6.44	3.00	6.4	3.0	Clarendon Lab.
1.62	7.14	2.77	7.16	2.75	Mean of Clarendon Lab. and N.P.L.
3.0	8.20	1.99	7.9	2.0	Figure 1, Report 7831.
3.7	8.48	1.70	8.2	1.7	"
5.0	8.69	1.31	8.6	1.3	"
10.0	8.78	0.70	8.8	0.7	"

The slightly low values of n in the observed column for $\lambda = 3$ and 3.7 are probably due to the fact that, when the n curve, Figure 1 of Report No. 7831, was constructed, there was only one observed value between $\lambda = 5$ and 2 cm. so that the curve has very little 'weight' in this region.

The agreement is so good that we are encouraged to use the Debye theory to predict n and χ at shorter wavelengths, for which no measurements are yet available.

Using the same constants as before we now obtain the values given in Table XV, which extends down to 1 mm. waves.

TABLE XV.

Values of the Constants Predicted
on the Debye Dipole Theory.
Water. 18° C.

λ cm.	n	$n\chi$	χ	g	h
0.1	1.93	1.28	0.665	2.08	4.96
0.2	2.58	1.91	.740	3.00	9.81
0.235	2.78	2.06	.742	3.49	11.46
0.3	3.13	2.30	.736	4.49	14.4
0.4	3.63	2.59	.713	6.49	18.8
0.5	4.08	2.78	.682	8.91	22.65
0.6	4.50	2.91	.649	11.64	26.18
0.7	4.86	3.00	.618	14.60	29.2
0.8	5.20	3.04	.587	17.74	31.8
0.9	5.52	3.085	.558	20.97	34.0
0.905	5.65	3.09	.547	22.3	34.94
1.0	5.79	3.08	.531	24.17	35.65
1.1	6.06	3.05	.504	27.37	37.0
1.2	6.33	3.03	.481	30.47	38.05

The predicted maximum of χ occurs at $\lambda = 0.235$ cm. and that of $n\chi$ at about $\lambda = 0.905$. The maximum of h is at $\lambda = 1.60$ and its value is then 39.5.

From the values in Table XV we find that C_2 diminishes from 2.541 at $\lambda = 1.0$ to 1.054 at $\lambda = 0.1$ cm. Similarly, C_3 varies from 1.225 at $\lambda = 1.0$ to 0.486 at $\lambda = 0.1$.

Now, provided that $C_3 \propto \lambda^3$ is much less than C_1 , the greatest value, D' , of D for which the error due to neglecting the terms above C_1 is 10% is given by

$$D' = \frac{\lambda}{\pi \sqrt{10}} \left(\frac{C_1}{C_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \dots\dots\dots(34)$$

From this we find that D' varies from 0.023 cm. for $\lambda = 1.0$ to 0.0083 cm. at $\lambda = 0.1$. But in clouds and fogs the droplet diameter D very seldom exceeds 0.005 cm. so that (15) will be valid even down to a wavelength of one millimetre. The resulting attenuation is given in Table XVI.

TABLE XVI.

Attenuation due to Clouds and Fogs
in the Millimetre Band.

Temp. 18° C.

Based on Constants from Debye Dipole Theory.

λ cm.	C_1	db./km. for $M = 1$
0.1	0.721	29.5
0.2	0.485	9.93
0.3	0.346	4.71
0.4	0.265	2.71
0.5	0.215	1.76
0.6	0.186	1.27
0.7	0.158	.925
0.8	0.136	.695
0.9	0.121	.550
1.0	0.1091	.446
1.1	0.0995	.369
1.2	0.0915	.311
1.3	0.0841	.264
1.4	0.0782	.228
1.5	0.0734	.199

It will be remembered that the attenuation is proportional to M and that $M = 1$ is a reasonable value for dense clouds and fogs, although it may be exceeded, see Section 9.

We conclude that the attenuation increases as the wavelength decreases, at least down to one millimetre.

TYPED BY: DB.
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